

Educational Discourses of Bangladesh: An Epistemological Evaluation of Primary Education

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Abstract:- The article concentrates on the overall general primary education system in Bangladesh, its background and present situation, donors' behavior, political culture, progress, and future education policy that was tried to show in the education plan. Quantitative education gets preference, and the curriculum's main job is to pass the students without quality learning in the formal schooling system. So, it has to create a third space to combine indigenous and western knowledge to give proper and quality education. Quantitative education needs to provide functional literacy, which can prepare good leaders, managers, and administrators. With an increasing functional literacy rate, a country can overcome cultural values, corruption, and intrinsic factors. In this essay, the researcher uses third-generation activity theory, models of management and leadership theory, and situational leadership model to combine indigenous and western knowledge systems to create a third space to overcome the present situation.

Keywords:- Epistemology, Innate, Culture, Attribution, Peasant, Indigenous, Transformational, Functional.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantitative and qualitative entry to knowledge is the key to skills formation and supreme to cultivating productivity. Therefore, education, which inspires and authorizes people to contribute to their development, is Bangladesh's most effective instrument for poverty reduction. Rahman, Hamzah, Meerah, and Rahman (2010) stated about the role of education in Bangladesh that,

Education is also heralded to reduce population growth, reduce maternal mortality, increase agricultural productivity, higher labor force participation, and lead to democratization. Investment in education makes a citizenry more committed to good governance, fiscal accountability, and transparency (p.114).

Quality education is a pivot of supportable development. Education permits individuals to improve within their community and country and agrees nations to contest and continue in the universal economy. Quality education plays a critical role in nurturing necessary well-informed abilities, growing further educational chances that are vigorous to

achieve in a world where power is thoroughly related to knowledge. World Bank's Learning for all Strategy 2020 mentioned that education is fundamental to development and growth. Access to education, a fundamental human right enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, is also a planned development investment. The human mind makes all other development achievements possible, from health advances and agricultural invention to structure creation and self-contained segment growth. For developing countries to reap these benefits fully—both by learning from the stock of global ideas and through innovation—they need to unleash the human mind's probable. Moreover, education is no better tool for doing so (WB, 2011, p. 1).

Bangladesh is a developing country in the world today. It is overwhelmed with the various problems encircling its social, political, and economic structures. The five decades since the country achieved independence have been distressing. Recurring political disturbances, natural disasters, dramatic social changes, and economic seizures contributed to the depressed nature of the life of everyday people. The loss of people lives in hopeless poverty in weak rural areas or impoverished urban slums. From these perspectives, there is no other way to rescue the country from the situation without quantitative and qualitative education. In this short article, investigator will discuss the educational discourses of Bangladesh at the primary level in the general education stream concerning context, culture, epistemology, and leadership.

II. THE CONTEXT AND CULTURE OF EDUCATION

Before discussing the present education system, let us go back to the colonial era of the Indian subcontinent in brief, West Pakistan (present Pakistan) and East Pakistan (Bangladesh). British Government in all terms of education were administered to the subcontinent, so they had to think differently. It was one of the significant causes of backwardness in schooling in Bangladesh. In 2014, Asim and Saha argued that most historians criticized the British educational system in Pakistan (East and West) and argued that it was designed against identity and interests. All the seven terms introduced by the British Government followed the backwardness of East and West Pakistan. Therefore, the

religious language had been forced to start its educational movements. These seven educational terms are social, economic, political, institutional, religious, legal, and economic impacts (p.87). As a result, the areas needed to be addressed in the British colonial era. British regime created identity conflict; hence they were attracted to religious education, which was written in Arabic, Persia, Urdu, and even though not in Bengali because Muslims believed that Bengali was the Hindus' language (Poet Abdul Hakim's (1620-1690) "Bangobani"). After the British colonial Period from 1947 to 1971, East Pakistan (Bangladesh) was West Pakistani (Pakistan) colony. When the Pakistani administration in West Pakistan made new primary schools, primary school goes increased significantly, whereas, in East Pakistan, both primary school and school goes decreased alternatively. The graph shows the primary school availability in East and West Pakistan from 1950 to 1971.

Fig. 1: School-going students aged 5-14 (Asadullah, 2010, p. 14)

After independence, from 1971 to 1991 army ruled the country except from 1971-1975, and there were various movements when the education system was not prioritized. Then overcoming the military regime, it returned to civil law in 1991, and Bangladesh started a multi-party parliamentary democratic system. However, the political culture and stability of democratic institutions have been marked since the beginning because of hostility and continuous violence between the two main political parties, namely the current ruling party Awami League (AL) and Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP). Both parties have dispositional attributions (attribution theory), so they cannot leave out their 'innate factors' (Bredlid, 2013). According to GEM Report (country case, 2017), the concentration of power in the hands of a few people or offices, factional politics in the institutions, and the absence of opposition from the Parliament leading to fragile checks and balances have had a severe impact on the policy domain (p.2). There was no accountability, quality monitoring, or equity and equality.

Fig. 2: GEM Report 2017 (Summary, p. 14).

A. The Educational Structure In Bangladesh

Education in Bangladesh has three main phases - primary, secondary, and higher education. Primary school is a 5-year cycle, whereas secondary education is a 7-year. There are three sub cycles in secondary education: junior secondary, three years; secondary education, two years; and higher secondary education (college), two years. The entry age for primary school is six years. The junior secondary 11-13 years, secondary 14-15, and higher secondary stage 16-17-year age are designed for students. Higher secondary is followed by higher education in general, technical, technology, and medical streams requiring 5 to 6 years to obtain a master's degree. According to National Education Policy (2010), primary education is an 8-year cycle, and secondary education is a 4-year cycle (p. 6, 14). However, it is still in progress. Bredlid (2005c) is interconnected with identity and curriculum. A national curriculum is making a national identity where specific cultural ethics are promoted while others are not. Such a selection is indeed very contentious because it most certainly means that the cultural heritage of many schoolchildren is not being valued (p. 251). If we create an excellent curriculum and education policy, we can make a national identity with a good education. The present education system in Bangladesh is a tradition from the British colonial Period. However, a new curriculum will be introduced in 2023 to a limited extent and will be implemented chronologically. There are a few streams of the education system in Bangladesh.

Fig. 3: Different Streams of Education System (Source: Rahman at el. 2010, p.125).

B. Primary Education System in Bangladesh

The administrative tasks in the education sector of Bangladesh, ranging from teacher recruitment and determination of curriculum to public examinations, are also centralized. Local administration, as well as public schools, have little or no autonomy over these decisions. Thus, the need for more resources and rigid centralization impedes the effective functioning of a mutual accountability system (GEM Report: Bangladesh 2017, p. 6).

Likewise, in the administrative structure of primary education in Bangladesh, where there is no contribution of teaching staff, they have no freedom to make any decision or even though they have no competency to teach well because of corrupted appointments. The top-down process and macro-level decision influence almost all fields of education in Bangladesh, and there is no combination. As a result, teaching staffs are not willing to teach well in their classroom; they pass their time when they take their classes or are absent from the course. Instead, we must create a third space to combine indigenous and Western knowledge, top-down and bottom-up, and macro and micro-level decisions. Finally, two interacting activity systems curriculum settlers can use as a minimal model for third-generation activity theory.

Fig. 4: Third-generation activity theory (source: Breidlid, 2013, p. 50).

Here the study will show the administrative structure of the Directorate of Primary Education (hereafter DPE). DPE consists of the following structure.

Fig. 5: Administration of primary education in Bangladesh (2018).

C. Drop-Out Rate in Primary Education

In Bangladesh, primary school students increased significantly, although quality did not increase. Functional literacy rate may be minimal, and many students need help to read or write well after completing standard four. The education for All (EFA) program partly fulfilled its target in Bangladesh to increase the number of schoolgoers. With the Government of Bangladesh, UNICEF is working to achieve education for all Bangladeshi children through the Second Primary Education Development Programme (PEDP II), which began in 2004. PEDP-II is a six-year-long coordinated and integrated sub-sector-wide program financed by the Government of Bangladesh and 11 development partners, including UNICEF. Due to its end in 2011, this program is being implemented in all 64 districts, covering 61,072 schools for a total cost of USD 1.8 billion. After finishing PEDP II, Primary Education Development Program III (PEDP III) has started the follow-on phase of Primary Education Development Program II, the Government's effort to provide quality education to all Bangladeshi children in every classroom. There is an increased focus on results in this new phase; as a result, the situation is changing daily and decreasing the drop-out rate.

Fig. 6: Year-wise drop-out rate 2005-2016 (source: DPE)

D. Indigenous Pieces of Knowledge And Sustainability

Bangladesh is a monoculture country, and there is no mentionable ethnic community. Ethnic populations are about 1.6 million, 1.10 percent of the total people.

Table 1: Ethnic population in Bangladesh

Ethnic Population		
Total Population (Enumerated)	15,86,141	1.10 (%National)
Male	7,97,477	50.28 (% of Ethnic Total)
Female	7,88,664	49.72 (% of Ethnic Total)
Total Household	3,56,175	1.11 (% National)

Source: BBS 2011

The Government took the initiative to include ethnic people to accommodate mainstream. National Education Policy 2010 (hereafter NEP) stated that,

Measures would be taken to ensure the availability of teachers from ethnic groups and to prepare texts in their languages so that ethnic children can learn their indigenous languages. In these initiatives, especially in preparing textbooks, the inclusion of respective indigenous communities will be ensured. Special assistance will be provided to

marginalized indigenous children. There are areas where the primary school needs to be present. Primary schools will be set up in these areas inhabited by ethnic people, both in hilly or plain lands. In some areas, there is a thin ethnic population. So, the schools may need more children. So, to create opportunities for the enrollment of a sufficient number of children, residential facilities for teachers and learners must be created (p. 8).

Moreover, Bangladeshi peasant culture has an active indigenous component, and their primary profession is cultivating various kinds of crops in their field. The Government of Bangladesh can follow the Cuban native knowledge system. Breidlid (2013) wrote that,

Over the past 25 years, Cuba has established advanced agricultural biotechnology and biopharmaceutical industry and has independently developed agricultural products, biopharmaceuticals, and bio-vaccines while retaining fundamental intellectual property rights. These can earn 100 million US dollars for Cuba annually (p. 143).

Similarly, the Government of Bangladesh emphasizes indigenous knowledge. For example, according to National Education Policy (2010), "to foster creativity and to think faculties among the learners through a system of education that contains native spirit and elements, and which will lead to a life-oriented development of knowledge of the learners" (p. 1). GoB is trying to achieve sustainable development goals; however, with its vast population and all levels of corruption, it takes more work to acquire the objectives. Here about 2000 people live per square kilometer.

Also, GoB has taken the initiative to reduce discrimination among children. Special provisions like free admission, free educational materials, free lunch at schools, and stipends will be arranged to attract and retain these (poor income group) children in the schools. Adequate measures will be taken for their safe protection within the schools (NEP 2010. p. 8). However, more is needed to build up a good nation. In a beautiful country, we need proper and quality education. Jones (2007) wrote,

Proper education that much conventional thinking about how knowledge might contribute to an ordered, peaceful, and productive world has centered on two principal assumptions—that education can contribute to peace, international understanding, and the promotion of human rights, and that knowledge can stimulate worker productivity, economic growth, and poverty reduction. In each case, the assumption rests on providing the 'right' kind of education; otherwise, education can fail in these objectives and run counter to them (p. 325).

GoB has taken steps to accommodate special children and mentioned in NEP 2010 that the lavatories' facilities and the smooth movement scope will be adequately designed and created with particular attention to fulfill the unique needs of the physically challenged learners. Special and privileged attention will be given to their needs. At least one trainer will be recruited in each of the PTIs to enable the unique teaching

methods and needs of various types of challenged learners (p. 8). However, GoB's hegemonic role destroys the NEP (2010). GEM report 2017 figured out the actual situation. New education policy has come into implementation and needs to be sufficiently reached by direct beneficiaries, i.e., students, parents, and teachers. For instance, the only option that kept giving feedback on the 'policy draft' was the ministry's website, which is not accessible to the people in hard-to-reach areas. Thus, the centralized system has created a 'black box' of the policy process that is only accessible to a few elites composed of the Government and occasionally some CSOs and donors.

Consequently, the implementation challenges of the new education policy, including the recent concerns about the negative impact of two additional public examinations in grade-5 and grade-8, imply that the decisions might not be aligned with the needs, capacity, and interests of relevant stakeholders. The frequent exams have not only impacted students by bringing in unhealthy competition but also led to an increasing practice of corruption in exams, including question leakage, copying, and other malpractices. As a result, the schooling system has become 'exam-centric' rather than 'learning-centric,' emphasizing achieving a good grade rather than gaining knowledge. Therefore, education goals, on the one hand, need to focus on individuals' interests sufficiently; on the other, they sometimes conflict with the Government's actions (p. 6-7).

Likewise, a monitoring system in the education sector in Bangladesh needs to be in the proper way, which is why teachers, principals, and officers of the education sector neglect their duties. GEM report 2017 showed that the internal monitoring system needs proper functioning; hence, teachers' performance could be better monitored. Therefore, teacher absenteeism, negligence of duties, and other irregularities are commonly practiced. For example, a study by the World Bank (2011) found that "on average, 15.5 percent of the primary school teachers are absent from their duties, which is even more prevalent in the case of head teachers" (p. 7).

There needs to be more independence over the teaching curricula because centralized decision-making procedures accompanied by the absence of an actual performance monitoring scheme generate a culture of apathy among beneficiaries to grasp teachers accountable.

E. Role of Donor Organizations

After finishing Primary Education Development Program II (PEDP) and achieving quantitative success, PEDP III is following phase II. There is an increased emphasis on results in this new stage. The program, which started on July 1, 2011, is being implemented over six years with the funding of some expansion associates, including the Asian Development Bank, AusAID, CIDA, DFID, EC, JICA, Netherlands, SIDA, UNICEF, and the World Bank/IDA. The development objectives of the projected program are to:

- raise the number of children enrolled and completed primary education,
- decrease social and regional disparities, and

- advance the measurement of student learning and the quality of the teaching and learning environment.
- Jones (2007) wrote about donor organizations,

Multilateral agencies, non-governmental organizations, professions, and scientific communities have all joined in a complete structure of global influence and engagement. Just one of many examples was the series of international conferences convened by the UN through the 1990s on themes actively promoted by NGOs and civil society: education for all, children's rights, the environment and development, human rights, population and development, social development, women, the habitat, and sustainable development. All of these were mounted through the organizations of political multilateralism. However, notably the Bretton Woods institutions actively pursued their conference agenda, addressing such issues as trade, debt, and development financing, again with unprecedented levels of NGO involvement (p. 330).

GEM report (country case, 2017) stated that government schools' increasing number of students in primary education, resulting from the MDGs, has made developing a system of mutual accountability among teachers, students, and parents more challenging. For example, Bangladesh has a high Student-Teacher Ratio (STR), with a headcount of 46 students per teacher in government-controlled schools, creating an ineffective learning environment (p. 6).

However, the education system of Bangladesh is continually undertaking restructurings to encounter the current and future needs and challenges of the country's socio-economic developments. In that sequence of modification, primary education has achieved many positive developments. Bangladesh has made significant progress in providing more young people with access to primary education, increasing enrolment, especially for girls, increasing the number of schools and teachers, reduction of gender disparity in education, and revision of curriculum. Despite all remarkable achievements, declining quality in the primary education system, reflected in public examination results, remains a significant concern. Bangladesh's Government ultimately recognizes the urgent need to recover the quality of education and its efforts to create equitable access to primary education. However, the issues of access, equity, and quality needing to be addressed have to be looked at collaboratively, and the strategies to address them must also look at the key areas simultaneously, not in a fragmentary fashion. More investment in this sector is needed, although some things could be improved, hindrances and a scarcity of financial resources. However, what is of interest to all stakeholders is identifying factors or variables that improve learning in all schools, irrespective of the background of the children that join them and are generalizable to all schools.

The School Management Committees (SMCs) could be more helpful. SMC members do not consider service receivers' concerns and are run mainly by unschooled and politically biased people. Furthermore, the ineffective application of the Right to Information Act-2009 needs to ensure that schools reveal all information regarding the responsibilities of

teachers, the decision-making process, the budget, and the expenses of schools. Accordingly, financially capable parents move to high-achieving schools with an adaptable management system. The situation exemplifies a sharp contrast between the *state's goals* and persons.

In contrast, the state emphasizes nation-building instruments, and individuals emphasize building personal abilities to be competent in the career market. GEM report (country case, 2017) showed that parents' involvement in children's education is vital for better outcomes. Schools have an even more critical role in monitoring students' progress through institutional mechanisms such as maintaining regular home-school diaries and contacting parents through home visits and telephone calls. However, these practices need to be revised in most public schools in Bangladesh. Though informal home visits of the teachers happened long before in the rural areas to urge parents about the student's learning progress, it does not occur nowadays thanks to the increasing number of students and low professional motivation resulting from low salaries and institutional focus on rules and duties rather than students' performance (p. 7). On the other hand, the successful implementation of a national development program depends on the effective allocation of resources in the respective sector. Although the size of the total budget is expanding, the overall allocation for the education sector of Bangladesh is increasing at a different rate. An analysis by UNICEF (2012) showed that,

While the total budget increased at an average rate of 28.7 percent between 2008-09 and 2012-13, the allocation for the education sector only increased by 20.1 percent in this Period. Besides, the share of the education budget in GDP is one of the lowest in the world. Bangladesh ranked third lowest among 78 countries, with only 1.97 percent of GDP spent on education in 2013, compared to 4.09 percent in Nepal, 2.50 in Pakistan, 4.54 in Afghanistan, and 5.59 in Bhutan (GEM report, p. 5).

Moreover, financial solvency, educational level, and parents' awareness also matter to perform their obligations towards schools and students' knowledge process. For instance, although schools sometimes take the initiative to hear parents' concerns through SMC, parents do not always reply, thinking that their responsibility is only sending children to school; the rest is the teachers', which depresses schools to take such initiatives. Poverty and less education are typical difficulties in performing the above responsibilities since poor parents need to concentrate more on supporting the family. Besides, parents (mostly mothers) with numerous responsibilities, i.e., work and domestic management, tend to invest less time in children's homes or engage with school advantages.

Likewise, Transparency International Bangladesh (TIB) finds teachers' recruitment as one of the primary sources of corruption in the education sector of Bangladesh. Among the types of corruption, discrimination and political relationship are common and influence teachers' recruitment and training processes. Also, UEO makes schools buy necessary materials from favored retailers, which leads to reduced quality

manufacture. Furthermore, the political inspiration from the local area, the flawed bidding process, short bidding periods, and confidentiality of the selection process create opportunities to bribe the UEO to get construction contracts and other forms of corruption. Teachers are even compulsory to pay bribes for elementary administrative tasks such as certificate attestation, leave adjustment, and pension.

Similarly, their transfer and training processes are not exempt from bribes. Additionally, non-registered schools often pay a hefty bribe to get government registration. Moreover, the dysfunctional administrative culture resulting from the failure to clearly define the responsibilities of employees alongside a widespread acceptance of corruption as a norm in institutions leads to the longevity of these irregularities, negatively affecting outcomes (GEM report, 2017).

III. EPISTEMOLOGY OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

In this section, the researcher will discuss the epistemology of the education system in Bangladesh. Breidlid (2013) defined epistemology as,

Epistemology refers to the word's traditional meaning, the theory of knowledge. Epistemology deals with questions of what knowledge is and how they are acquired- in other words, the nature, scope, and sources of knowledge. Epistemology is how people view and make sense of the world according to what they have learned and believe (p. 2).

He related epistemology and the global architecture of education, an everyday epistemological discourse. The global architecture of education dominates great educational systems in the global South.

The educational system of Bangladesh is borrowed from Western epistemology because of poverty. From the colonial Period, its education system was neglected, and after the demise of the colonist, the people of Bangladesh decolonized their minds (Ngugi Wa Thiong O'). Donors dependency is one of those. Brock-Utne (2000) gave an example from her African friend that is equally true about Bangladesh,

While many of my African friends have told me that the World Bank intends to recolonize Africa by giving Africans only a poor and rudimentary education and letting advanced knowledge belong to the West, I do not believe this is the intention of World Bank planners- but it might well be the effect (p. 12).

So far, World Bank, MDG, ADB, UNICEF, and JICA's education for all was quantitative, not qualitative. However, WB's current slogan is quality education for all. Learning for All means ensuring that all students, not just the most privileged, acquire the knowledge and skills they need to live happy, productive lives (WB, 2011). However, education is comparatively more essential in less developed countries, at least primary education. Saha (1983) wrote that minimum education and literacy were essential for modernization and

industrialization, specifically for less developed countries. Thus, during the Period following World War II, we entered what has rightfully been called the age of innocence, which manifested in a worldwide explosion in educational enrolments and expenditure in developed and less-developed countries. Concerning the latter, attaining a literate population employing universal primary education became a significant goal for many development programs (chapt 2, p. 40).

More than a literacy rate is needed nowadays; we need to develop a functional literacy rate. We must amend various ideological and epistemological knowledge to increase the functional literacy rate. Solely functionally literate people can overcome cultural and epistemological boundaries. So, Steiner-Khamsi (2014) criticized the international educational politics that the terms "international standards," "21st-century skills", and "best practices" powerfully resonate with politicians and policymakers, and they resort to them at particular moments of agenda setting: whenever there is a need to generate reform pressure. Despite no agreement on what they mean, these terms effectively function as catalysts for change. Even better, they serve as empty vessels that are, whenever needed, filled with local meaning. Nevertheless, they are politically powerful because they generate fears of falling behind in a global marketplace and therefore have the potential to build, as mentioned before, coalitions among interest groups that otherwise would be opposing each other (p. 156-7).

Similarly, Breidlid (2013) stated that "Western Knowledge has not been developed in a vacuum, but its trajectory is inextricably linked to the spread of colonialism and capitalism and the dislocation of other epistemologies" (p. 5). Likewise, modernity has been associated with capitalism and westernization in that "progress has therefore also been linked to modernization, most often defined in opposition to tradition ."Westernization has therefore gained the status of a universal goal and destiny. As may be seen today, the epistemological consequence is a tendency to create a dichotomy between modernity and tradition, indigenous and western knowledge. As stated by Du Plessis, traditional or established knowledge also carries the understanding of being universal. If we want to be serious and implement the global UN objectives focusing on Education for Sustainable Development, this understanding has to be reversed. In the following section, the Education for Sustainable Development concept will be further elaborated to frame Engeström's theory of expansive learning in sustainable development (Ellen, 2013, p. 3453).

According to Breidlid (2013), sustainable development is almost entirely centered on a western epistemological and ideological framework as discussed among the UN organizations. The Johannesburg Declaration of Education for Sustainable Development focused on eradicating poverty and achieving a fair resource allocation. However, education and training were referred to together with "Technology transfers, human resource development, education and training to banish underdevelopment forever" (p. 70). Education was also noted as essential to mobilize natural resources and critical for promoting sustainable development. The Declaration has also

underlined the importance of the environment in sustainable development. It implies that Indigenous knowledge must be seen from this perspective. But Breidlid raises an important issue when he asks; "How do the educational inputs promote sustainable development?" (Ellen, 2013, p. 353) Human is the key to national development, in his human development theory, Saha, L. J (1983) wrote that.

While modernization theory dominated the thinking and research of sociologists, economists also formulated their theory of development based on structural-functional notions. Modernization theory for sociologists was mainly a social psychological theory focusing on individual values and attitudes. The economists, however, focused on the productive capacity of the human workforce in the development process and, in so doing, treated the human workforce's improvement as a form of capital investment. Thus, the human capital theory postulates that the most efficient path to any society's national development lies in improving its population, that is, its human capital (p. 18).

He (1983) also argued that one of the first systematic articulations of human capital theory occurred in 1960 when Theodore Schultz made his presidential address. Schultz stated that education was not to be viewed simply as a form of consumption but instead as a productive investment. He argued that education improves the individual choices available to men and that an educated population provides the labor force necessary for industrial development and economic growth. As with modernization theory, human capital theory provided a fundamental justification for sizeable public expenditure on education in developed and developing nations. The method was stable with the ideologies of democracy and liberal progressivism found in most Western societies (p.19).

IV. LEADERSHIP AND EDUCATION

The quality of leadership generates a significant difference in school and student outcomes. In many parts of the globe, comprising both developed and developing countries, there is the perception that schools need influential leaders, managers, and administration to deliver the best possible education for their students and learners. As the global economy folds, more governments realize that their primary resources are their people and that staying, becoming, and being competitive depends increasingly on developing highly skilled staff. It requires trained and dedicated teachers but essential the leadership of instrumental principals with the cooperation of other senior and middle managers. Bush (2008) mentioned practical and essential leadership components that vision is increasingly regarded as an essential component of effective leadership. Emerging generalizations about leadership, four of which relate directly to vision:

- Outstanding leaders have a vision for their organizations.
- Vision must be communicated in a way that secures commitment among members of the organization.
- Communication of vision requires communication of meaning.
- Attention should be given to institutionalizing vision if leadership is to be successful. (p. 3).

Leadership, management, and administration, these three concepts are interrelated. Models of management and leadership theory are given below:

Table 2: Models of management and leadership theory (Source: Bush 2008, p. 10).

Management Model	Leadership Model
Formal	Managerial
Collegial	Participative
	Transformational
	Interpersonal
Political	Transactional
Subjective	Postmodern
Ambiguity	Contingency
Cultural	Moral
	Instructional

Coleman and Earley (2005) mentioned Leidhood et al.'s six leadership categories, which represent leadership models in education today. Each style has a different focus. The leadership styles are defined in terms of influence: who is exerting it, what is it exerted for, and what are its outcomes.

The categories are:

- Instructional: the critical focus is the learning of their (teachers) students and the effectiveness of teachers' expertise.
- Transformational: building capacity in the organization.
- Moral leader: focus on values in leadership and aims
- Participative: sharing of decision-making within the educational institution in a democratic way
- Managerial: it is also called technical, formal, or task-oriented leadership. The aim is for the efficient achievement of goals.
- Contingent: variation in response to different leadership situations for increasing the organization's capacity for change.

❖ *A Case Study of a School in Bangladesh:*

When the researcher was in Bangladesh, he worked in a school. Head-teacher used to arrange teachers' meetings twice a month. The purpose of the meeting was to deliver his guidelines to the teachers. However, he should have asked the teachers how to increase our teaching style or develop our institution. He used to supply only his decisions. As a result, teachers in the meeting were listeners (receivers), and the head teacher was the speaker (supplier); there was no give-and-take policy among them. After ending the meeting, teachers forgot about it and worked with their previous styles. So, there still needed to be an outcome. This kind of leadership cannot give anything to the institution or the country's education system.

A. Culture and Leadership

Coleman and Earley (2005) mentioned Hofstede's onion metaphor to discuss culture and leadership. One peels away the outer layers of an onion, and more of what is hidden inside is revealed. The culture onion's outer, more visible layers are concerned with symbols and practices, while the concealed innermost layer consists of values. The outer layer is relatively easy to understand, and the core values are usually hidden; these are the assumptions inherent in the culture. The inner

core of cultural values is transmitted from generation to generation, with the responsibility given to parents, teachers, religious leaders, and other respected elders in the community. At the age of ten, most children have their basic value system firmly in place, and then changes are difficult to make after that age. Values and culture may be derived from the national or ethnic group, generation, work organization, gender, class, and religion (p. 29). Culture is the mind's collective programming that distinguishes one group of people from another. Coleman and Earley (2005) defined the characteristics of culture:

- Culture consists of ideals, values, and assumptions about life that guide specific behaviors.
- Culture consists of those aspects of the environment that people make.
- Culture is transmitted from generation to generation, with the responsibility given to parents, teachers, religious leaders, and other respected elders in the community (p. 30).
- No culture is easily changeable because culture represents values. The education system also depends upon culture and values. So, it is not too easy to change the education system like Bangladesh; it is related to culture and values.

B. The Situational Leadership Models

Coleman and Earley (2005) discussed Hersey's situational leadership model. It gives managers a structured approach to flexible leadership tailored to each team member, depending on the level of readiness or development of each. The leader is encouraged to provide the right leadership style for a specific individual or task. The readiness level is found by analyzing the relative combination of competence and commitment. The most appropriate leadership style (telling, selling, participating, or delegating) is then selected for that individual for the task in question (p. 38).

Fig. 7: Situational leadership model (source: Coleman & Earley 2005, p. 39).

For example, from figure 7, if someone's readiness level is identified as R1, s/he would need more help from the leader. The most appropriate style to use with this person for this task would be the directive style of 'telling.' Leaders can go incrementally so that separate team followers can steadily mature by improving their development stages from R1 to R2 and R3 to R4 (Coleman & Earley, 2005). From the perspective of Bangladesh, most of the employees are R1, so they need help from the leader to reach R2. At least Bangladesh needs good leadership, and it is essential to improve educational

institutions or education systems from education policy to classroom implementation.

V. CONCLUSION

The study has figured out the overall general stream primary education system of Bangladesh, its background, donors' behavior so far, its progress, and future education policy, which GoB tried to show in the education plan. Quantitative education gets preference in Bangladesh, and the curriculum's primary job is to pass the students, not quality learning in the formal schooling system. Evidence suggests that the formal school curriculum's primary emphasis is on passing examinations and obtaining certificates for job allocation. To educate a million, we have to create systems and institutions. We need to grade, certify, and arrange exams and diplomas — and that is where the problem arises because grading, approving, and awarding diplomas can overshadow the business of educating (Carm, 2013). Research already mentioned that Bangladesh must find a third space to combine indigenous and western knowledge, top-down and bottom-up, and macro and the micro-level decision to give proper and quality education. A new curriculum has arrived in Bangladesh to a limited extent by creating a third space to combine indigenous and western knowledge systems. It is possible to change the education culture and values to create identity by removing corruption. Finally, there may be importance in culture, context, epistemology, leadership, and more research about quality education in Bangladesh.

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